

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PLANT PROTECTION AND QUARANTINE IN ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGES (SOIL AND OTHER FACTORS) UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771611>

Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of global climate change on the environment, particularly soil fertility, water resources, and the state of ecosystems. The role and importance of plant protection and quarantine in the context of climate change in maintaining plant health, sustainable agricultural development, and ensuring food security will also be considered. The article discusses the prevention of the spread of new pests and diseases caused by climate change, strategies to combat them, and the need for quarantine measures.

Keywords: Global climate change, plant protection, plant quarantine, environmental change, soil fertility, pests, diseases, sustainable agriculture, food security.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется влияние глобального изменения климата на окружающую среду, в частности на плодородие почв, водные ресурсы и состояние экосистем. Также будет рассмотрена роль и значение защиты растений и карантина в сохранении здоровья растений, устойчивом развитии сельского хозяйства и обеспечении продовольственной безопасности в условиях изменения климата. В статье обсуждается предотвращение распространения новых вредителей и болезней, вызванных изменением климата, стратегии борьбы с ними и необходимость карантинных мер.

Ключевые слова: Глобальное изменение климата, защита растений, карантин растений, изменение окружающей среды, плодородие почвы, вредители, болезни, устойчивое сельское хозяйство, продовольственная безопасность.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola global iqlim o'zgarishining atrof-muhitga, xususan tuproq unumdorligi, suv resurslari va ekotizimlar holatiga ta'sirini tahlil qiladi. Shuningdek, iqlim o'zgarishi sharoitida o'simliklar himoyasi va karantini sohasining o'simliklar salomatligini saqlash, qishloq xo'jaligini

barqaror rivojlantirish va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashdagi o'rni va ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada iqlim o'zgarishi tufayli yuzaga keladigan yangi zararkunandalar va kasalliklar tarqalishining oldini olish, ularga qarshi kurashish strategiyalari va karantin tadbirlarining zarurligi muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Global iqlim o'zgarishi, o'simliklar himoyasi, o'simliklar karantini, atrof-muhit o'zgarishi, tuproq unumdorligi, zararkunandalar, kasalliklar, barqaror qishloq xo'jaligi, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi.

Today, the world community recognizes that climate change is the most serious problem facing humanity. Climate change affects all spheres of human life and requires urgent measures to prevent the negative consequences of climate change and adapt to new living conditions. Modern science provides serious grounds to confirm that human economic activity, primarily associated with the release of greenhouse gases as a result of burning fossil fuels, has a significant impact on the climate. In Uzbekistan, from 1880 to the present, the average annual temperature increased by 1.6 degrees (from 13.2 to 14.8 °C), which is higher than the global average. According to experts' forecasts, in 2030-2050, the air temperature in the region may rise by another 1.5-3°C. Temperatures are expected to rise, especially in the Aral Sea region, which will be exacerbated by local climate change. Uzbekistan is among the countries most vulnerable to the consequences of climate change. According to expert assessments, a further increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere will lead to an increase in the risk of water and food shortages as a result of drought, an increase in the population due to an increase in the duration and intensity of the hot season, as well as the recurrence of mudflows, floods, and other dangerous phenomena. Moreover, such warming negatively affects the state of ecosystems and leads to an exacerbation of the ecological situation in such regions as the Aral Sea region, Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya, Bukhara, and Khorezm regions. Global climate change and the sensitivity of the country's natural resource complex to these changes determine the need to form a consistent climate policy. Impact of environmental change on plants. Climate change directly affects the physicochemical properties of the soil. Increased temperature leads to faster decomposition of organic matter in the soil, which leads to a decrease in fertility. Drought increases water scarcity, and floods intensify soil erosion. In addition, climate change can expand the distribution areas of pests and diseases, increase the rate of their development, and reduce plant resistance to them. Extreme weather events directly harm plants.

Summary: Global climate change is having a serious impact on the environment, in particular on soil and other factors important for agriculture. In these conditions, the field of plant protection and quarantine is crucial for maintaining plant health, ensuring yields, and guaranteeing food security. Increasing investment in these sectors, introducing modern technologies, and strengthening international cooperation will contribute to mitigating the negative consequences of climate change and developing sustainable agriculture.

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